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PARIPLUTA YONIVYAPAD: ACCORDING TO AYURVEDA AND ITS MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

A healthy woman is a promise to a healthy family & woman's health status is a complex arrangement controlled by a range of factors headed by her reproductive system. Infections about *Yoni* are a burning problem for women irrespective of their age & socio-economic status. It becomes very irritating for the woman as it affects her concentration & hampers her day-to-day life. It may lead to psychological upset, and depression and thus affects a woman's personality. In Ayurveda, gynaecological disorders have found immense importance in medicine because women have that unique ability to give birth. In Ayurveda, women's healthcare is described in a separate section under the name of *yonivyapad*, including a majority of gynaecological disorders. In *Paripluta yonivyapad* there is vitiation of *vata-pitta*. An increase in *pitta* causes *atiraktastrava*, *nila peeta yonistrava* and *jwara* whereas an abnormal increase of *vata* causes *shoola*. The Ayurvedic treatment not only cures pathology in reproductive organs but also treats the woman as a whole with a holistic approach, thereby improving her general health also. Before going to management of the disease literature of the disease should be known. Hence, a study effort has been put forth to make a literary study covering almost all aspects of *Paripluta yonivyapad* as per Ayurveda.

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INTRODUCTION

The present era is advanced and competitive, in this competitive world women are trying in many fields equally with men. To withstand in this competition and to achieve her goals she should be in her perfect health condition, particularly in terms of her reproductive healthiness.

A woman undergoes various physiological changes during her reproductive life span. Ayurveda stresses the importance of the health of women as she only can procreate and thus lay the foundation of a healthy society.

Any disorder which hampers the general, mental as well as reproductive health of a woman should be considered with care and require medical attention. Vaginal discharge is one of the most common problems faced by many women. Women don't give much attention towards this unless and until it makes them feel uncomfortable in this day-to-day life.

Paripluta yonivyapad is disease seen in women of reproductive age group. Many women have silent clinical features of *Paripluta* which has effect on her personal, interpersonal relationship between husband and wife. Main characteristic features seen are *atiraktastrava*, *nila peeta yonistrava* and *jwara* in case of increase in *pitta* and *shoola* in abnormal increase of *vata* along with other *vata lakshana*.

In this study, an effort has been put forth to make a conceptual study covering almost all the aspects of *Paripluta Yonivyapad*.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To study *Paripluta yonivyapad* in detail according to Ayurveda, literary study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This conceptual study is made after reviewing all the available Ayurveda classics thoroughly.

DESCRIPTION

In accordance with *Maharshi Charaka*, *Paripluta Yonivyapad* is caused by vitiation of *Vata* (air) and *Pitta* (bile) *Dosha*, characterized by inflammation of *yonis*, tenderness, painful menstruation, yellowish or bluish color of menstrual blood, pain in lumbosacral and groin region, backache and fever.¹

पित्तलाया नृसंवासे क्षवथुद्धारधरणात्। पित्तसम्मूच्छितं वायुर्योनिं दूषयति स्त्रियाः ।

शूना स्पाक्षमा सार्तिर्नीलपीतमसृक् स्रवेत्। श्रोणिवङ्क्षणपृष्ठार्तिज्वसर्तायाः परिप्लुता॥ च.चि.

३०/२३/२४

Sushruta says that the condition is characterized with severe dyspareunia, besides other pain and ache etc. caused by vitiated *Vayu* are also present.²

परिप्लुतायां भवति ग्राम्यधर्मे रुजा भृशम् | चतसृष्वपि चाद्यासु भवन्त्यनिलवेदनाः ॥ सु.उ.३८/१०-११

Both the *Vagbhatas* have followed *Charaka*; however they have included heaviness in the regions of bladder and lower abdomen, diarrhea and anorexia etc. also in the list of symptoms.³

पित्तलायाः नृसंवासे क्षवथु उदगार धारणात्। पित्त युक्तेन मारुता योनिः भवति दूषिता ॥

शूना स्पर्शासहा सार्ति नील पीतास वाहिनी । वस्ति कुक्षि गुरुत्व अतिसार अरोचक कारिणी ॥
श्रोणि वङ्क्षण रुक् तोद ज्वर कृत् सा परिप्लुता । अ. संउ. ३८/४८, अ.ह. उ. ३३ / ४६-४८

Madhava Nidana, Bhavprakasha and Yogaratnakara etc. have followed *Sushruta*.

In *Madhukosha* commentary it is explained that since, in this condition, the features of *Vata* i.e. pain etc. are present with extreme severity (*Pluta*) and all around (*Pari*) i.e. in entire internal and external reproductive organs, hence it is termed as *Paripluta*.⁴

NIDANA

Samanaya Hetu (nonspecific aetiology) of Paripluta Yonivyapad:

Mithyachara (including abnormal diet and abnormal mode of life), *Pradushta Artava* (hormonal disorders), *Bija Dosha* (abnormalities of sperm and ova), Excessive indulgence in coitus, *Daiva Prakopa* (idiopathic), *Apadravya Prayoga* (use of iron objects for sexual pleasure) etc.

Vishesha Hetu:

Maharshi Charaka and *Vagbhata* have discussed the *Vishesha Nidana* (specific aetiology) of *Paripluta*. *Charaka* and *Vagbhata* consider it as a *Vata-Pittaja Vyadhi* while *Sushruta* has mentioned it as a *Vataja Vyadhi*.

- *Pittala* – It means women having a predominance of *Pitta* due to her *Pitta Prakriti* and consumption of diet which exaggerates *Pitta*.
- *Pitta Prakriti*: Women having *Pitta Prakriti* develop *Pittaja Roga* quickly even by less etiological factors (*Alpa Nidana Sevana*) and the *Roga* are *Kashtasadhya*.
- The word '*Nrisamvaase*' shows that in the causation of this disease coitus (due to excessive coitus, coitus in an abnormal position) is a very important cause.
- *Swayathu-Udgara Dharanata*: In *Charaka Sutrasthana* the description of *Adharniya Vega* and its results are mentioned. Suppression of natural urges leads to *Vata Prokopa* but the urges mentioned in *Paripluta Yonivyapad* have no direct relation to the causation of this disease. So, we can conclude that by mentioning the two *Vega*, other *Adharniya Vega* should be considered and all these lead to *Vata Prokopa*.
- Since *Shotha* is a very important feature of *Paripluta Yonivyapad* we should also know about *Shotha Nidana* which is explained by *Acharya Charaka* in *Sutrasthana*, 18th chapter, *Trishothiya Adhyaya*.

Samprapti of Paripluta

Nrisamvaase (excessive coitus) + *Swayathu-Udgara* or any *Vega Dharana*+*Mithya Achara*

Dosha- Vaishamyia (*Apana Vata & Pitta Prakopa*) + Decreased immunity

Doshas Vitiata Dushya (*Rakta & Mamsa*)

Reaches the site of *Kha-Vaigunya* with *Rasavaha*, *Raktavaha*, *Artavavaha Srotas*

Kshubdha Yoni

Disturbance of the normal defense mechanism of *Yoni*
(*Vyadhikshamatva*) *Krimi*/micro-organisms

Paripluta Yonivyapad/ Pelvic Inflammatory Disease

Symptoms / Rupa of *Paripluta Yonivyapada*

In *Paripluta yonivyapad* there is vitiation of *vata-pitta*. Increase in amount of *pitta* causes *atiraktastrava*, *nila peeta yonistrava* and *jwara* whereas abnormal increase of *vata* causes *shoola*. The symptoms of *paripluta yonivyapad* are^{5,6,7}

- *Yonishoola/ Yonishotha*- vagina/uterus gets inflamed
- *Yonisparsha asakshama*- tenderness in vagina/uterus
- *Nila-peeta yonistrava*- painful menstruation having yellowish or bluish discoloration of menstrual blood.
- *Shronimandal vedana*- severe pain in lumbo-sacral, pelvis and groin, backache
- *Jwara* – fever
- *Vankshanapradesh vedana*

Other symptoms include

- *Gramya dharme ruja bhrusham*- severe pain during coitus (*Sushruta*)
- *Anil vedana*- pain, ache etc. symptoms caused by vitiated *vata* (*Sushruta*)
- *Vasti kukshi gurutwam*- heaviness in urinary bladder and lower abdomen (*Vagbhata*)
- *Arochaka*- anorexia (*Vagbhata*)
- *Atisara*- diarrhea (*Vagbhata*)
- *Gramya dharme ruchih*- interest for coitus (*Madhukosha*)

Complications (*Upadrava*) of *Paripluta Yonivyapad*

Acharya Charaka has described that when *Yoni* (reproductive system) of women afflicted with *Dosha* or diseases, doesn't retain *Shukra* (sperms) or the females become infertile, besides she also suffer from *Gulma*, *Arsha*, *Pradara* (menometrorrhagia) & other diseases of *Vata*.⁸

MANAGEMENT

Panchawalkal kwatha: According to *Charaka*, *kashaya rasa* has properties like, *shoshan*, *samgrahi*, *stambhana*⁹. It has quality of drying *kleda*. So it stops *strava*, *kashayarasa*, is mainly formed by conjugation of *Vayu* (air) and *prithvi mahabhuta*. *Vayu* is *ruksha* in quality and dries up the excessive fluids in tissues, while *prithvi* by virtue of *Katina* and *sthira guna* which are opposite of *Drava* and *Sara guna*.

Table NO. 1¹⁰

<i>Kanchnar Guggulu</i>	<i>Shothahara, vrana ropana, galganda, apache, arbuda, granthi, gulma, kushta, bhagandhara.</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Muscle relaxant, Antibacterial, Anticancer, Anti-tumor, Thyroid stimulant, Analgesic, Anti-mutagenic.
<i>Pushyanug Churna</i>	<i>Vrana Ropana, Krimighna, Rakta Shodhaka, Pittaghna, Artava Janana, Shothaghna Pachana, Vedanastapana, Rasayana, Garbhashaya Shodhaka, Pradarahara, Balya, Deepana, Jwarahara</i>	Immune stimulant, Amoebicidal Diuretic, Anti inflammatory, Anti bacterial, Anti spasmodic, Uterine stimulant, Antioxidant, Anti pyretic, Analgesic, Anti-ulcerogenic, Antiseptic, Anti helminthic
<i>Chandraprabha Vati</i>	<i>Balya, Vrushya, Sarwa Rogpranashini, tridosha nashak.</i>	Antacid, Anti-inflammatory, Anti-arthritic, Digestive Stimulant, Hematinic, Fat burner, anti-gout, Analgesic, Muscle relaxant, Anti-helminthic, mild anti-hypertensive.
<i>Dashmula kwath</i>	<i>Shothaghna, Jwaraghna, Shula Prashamana, Mutrala, Vrana Ropana, Vatashamana</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Antibacterial, Anti-pyretic, Spasmolytic, Uterine Stimulant

Tikta rasa has *krimighna* property which direct inhibits growth of *krimi* and finally diminishes *strava*. On the basis of research carried out on ingredients of *panchavalkala taila*, it has been postulated pharmacological properties, like anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antiprotozoal, antibacterial are present which cure pelvic inflammatory disease.

Yashtimadhu ghruta

The drug possesses karma like *shothahara* (anti-inflammatory) & *ropana* (healing). It's having *sheetaveerya, vata-pitta hara* property which helps to reduce *Shoona, Sparsha-ashatwa, mutradaha* & *gramyadharme ruja, vedana* in *shroni, vamkshana, prushta, kati*.¹¹

DISCUSSION

This disease can be cured mainly by taking hygiene. Personal hygiene is very important for every woman. Vaginal problems are mainly due to disturbances of vaginal flora. So, approach should be done to correct vaginal flora by which one can get rid of vaginal problems.

CONCLUSION

Paripluta yonivyapad is commonest problem in women during her reproductive age. As per Ayurveda, by maintaining proper hygiene, taking proper diet and exercise can help to maintain the reproductive health. It is seen that the same *yonivyapad* explained differently by different *Samhitas* represents the chronicity of a single disease. Hence instead of going with description of single *Samhita*, analyzing explanations given in all other *Samhitas* help us to understand pathogenesis and treatment of analyzing explanations given in all other *Samhitas* help us to understand pathogenesis and treatment of *Paripluta yonivyapad* in detail.

REFERENCES

1. *Agnivesh*, Revised by Charaka and Dridhabala, Introduction by Sri Satyanarayan Shastri, Charaka Samhita, Vidyotini Hindi Commentary, Chikitsa Sthana, 30/37-39, Chaukhamba Bharti Academy, Varanasi, Vol-2, Reprint: 2009, p.846
2. *Sushruta Samhita Ayurvedatatwasamdeepika* by kaviraj Ambikadatta Shastri Published by Chaukhamba prakashana Uttar Sthana chapter no.38 shloka no.10,11
3. *Ashtang sangraha Samhita* by Acharya Vagbhata Published by Chaukhamba prakashana Uttar Sthana chapter no.38shloka no.48 7.
4. Madhava Nidana Madhukosha vyakhya
5. *Ashtang sangraha Samhita* by Acharya Vagbhata Published by Chaukhamba prakashana Uttar Sthana chapter no.38shloka no.48 7.
6. *Sushruta Samhita Ayurvedatatwasamdeepika* by kaviraj Ambikadatta Shastri Published by Chaukhamba prakashana Uttar Sthana chapter no.38 shloka no.10,11
7. *Charak Samhita Agnivesh pratisanskrita* Published by Chaukhamba prakashana chikitsa Sthana chapter no.30shloka no.23,24
8. *Ashtang sangraha Samhita* by Acharya Vagbhata Published by Chaukhamba prakashana Uttar Sthana chapter no.39shloka no.49 page no.107
9. *Agnivesh*, Revised by Charka and Dridhabala, Introduction by Sri Satyanarayan Shastri, Charaka Samhita, Vidyotini Hindi Commentary, Chikitsa Sthana, 30/37-39, Chaukhamba Bharti Academy, Varanasi, Vol-2, Reprint: 2009, p.846
10. Dr. Ruchita shah Dr Veena Jawale Ayurvedic management of PID (*paripluta Yonivyapad*) - a case study published in PARIPEX - INDIAN JOURNAL OF RESEARCH Volume-9 Issue-3 March-2020
11. Prathima A H M , Sucheta Kumai M Clinical study of *paripluta yonivyapad* with Yashtimadhu Ghrita yoni pichu w.s.r to pelvic inflammatory disease published in International Ayurvedic medical journal